

Evaluating Fire Preparedness and Mitigation in Nigeria Oil and Gas Industry

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Abstract

The Nigerian oil and gas industry is central to the nation's economy but remains highly vulnerable to fire hazards that threaten lives, assets, and the environment. This study assessed fire preparedness and mitigation practices across selected oil and gas facilities, focusing on employee awareness, safety infrastructure, management commitment, and regulatory compliance. A cross-sectional survey of 350 employees yielded 211 valid responses, analyzed using SPSS with descriptive statistics and chi-square tests. Real-time air quality monitoring was conducted at a crude oil facility in Nigeria, using a portable Hanna handheld device to ensure accuracy. The measurements were taken across key operational areas, including the administrative building and various engineering departments, with the facility's name kept anonymous. Results revealed encouraging levels of preparedness: 76.2% of workers reported adequate fire safety training, 82.2% confirmed access to safety equipment, and 85.5% acknowledged routine fire drills. Strong management commitment and regulatory compliance were also affirmed, with over 90% of respondents citing the presence of dedicated safety officers, budgetary allocations, and environmental protection measures. However, gaps persisted; 23.8% of staff felt inadequately trained, 18% lacked clarity on muster points, and 15% reported the absence of safety plans in their facilities. Chi-square analysis showed significant associations between years of experience, frequency of drills, and the effectiveness of fire contingency plans, indicating the importance of both human and organizational factors. The research shows that enhancing fire preparedness in Nigeria's oil and gas industry requires continuous training, standardized drills, and strict maintenance of suppression systems.

Keywords: *Fire preparedness, oil and gas industry, Nigeria, safety training, emergency response, regulatory compliance.*

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Introduction

Fire incidents in the global oil and gas industry pose a formidable threat, with the potential to unleash catastrophic consequences on human lives, critical infrastructure, and the environment. Operating in high-risk environments characterized by flammable hydrocarbons, complex machinery, and high-pressure systems, the sector is inherently vulnerable to fires and explosions, as evidenced by landmark disasters like the 1988 Piper Alpha tragedy in the North Sea and the 2010 Deepwater Horizon explosion

in the Gulf of Mexico (Kerin, 2016). These incidents highlight the dire need for robust fire preparedness and mitigation strategies to prevent loss of life, economic disruption, and environmental devastation. In Nigeria, a key player in global oil production, the industry's significance is amplified by its role as the nation's economic cornerstone, contributing approximately 90% of export earnings and over 70% of government revenue (Hassan, 2021). The global imperative to enhance fire safety is particularly pressing in Nigeria, where unique operational challenges and environmental sensitivities necessitate tailored approaches to safeguard personnel, assets, and ecosystems from fire-related risks.

The Nigerian oil and gas industry, predominantly located in the Niger Delta, operates within a complex and high-stakes environment where fire hazards are made likely by aging infrastructure, tropical climatic conditions, and intricate operational processes. Historical fire incidents, such as the 2012 Chevron Escravos Gas Plant fire and the 2016 Agip Brass Oil Export Terminal blaze, shows the sector's vulnerability, resulting in significant financial losses, environmental damage, and threats to worker safety (Oluyemi, 2020; Wood et al., 2012). These incidents stem from a confluence of technical failures (equipment corrosion), operational lapses (inadequate maintenance), and human errors (procedural deviations), highlighting the need for fire safety measures tailored to Nigeria's context (Ambituuni et al., 2014; Fadeyibi et al., 2011; Nwankwo et al., 2022). The industry's extensive infrastructure, including offshore platforms, refineries, and pipelines, amplifies the potential impact of fires, making effective preparedness and mitigation critical to sustaining operations and protecting surrounding communities and ecosystems.

The significance of this research lies in its potential to report critical safety, economic, and environmental challenges within the Nigerian oil and gas industry. From a safety perspective, robust fire preparedness protects workers, fostering a secure working environment and enhancing morale and productivity (Slil et al., 2025). Economically, effective fire mitigation minimizes disruptions to production, reduces financial losses, and preserves Nigeria's substantial contribution to GDP, which stood at 35% from the oil and gas sector in 2021 (Abu et al., 2023). Environmentally, preventing fire-related incidents like oil spills and air pollution safeguards the ecologically sensitive Niger Delta, aligning with sustainable development goals (Srivastava, 2020). Furthermore, a strong fire safety record enhances the industry's global reputation, attracting foreign investment and fostering international partnerships. By identifying gaps in current practices and proposing evidence-based improvements, this study seeks to strengthen the sector's resilience, ensuring operational continuity and societal benefits.

Existing literature on fire preparedness in the Nigerian oil and gas industry reveals a foundation of regulatory frameworks and international standards yet highlights persistent implementation challenges (Ambituuni et al., 2014; Dhali et al., 2023; Olujobi & Ape, 2025). The Petroleum (Drilling and Production) Regulations of 1969 and the Oil Pipeline Act of 1990 mandate safety protocols and emergency response plans, while global guidelines from the American Petroleum Institute (API) and the International Association of Oil & Gas Producers (IOGP) provide best practices for fire risk management. However, studies suggest that these standards are not consistently applied due to factors such as inadequate training, irregular maintenance, and weak regulatory enforcement (Ambituuni et al., 2014; Babalola & Olawuyi, 2022; Fadeyibi et al., 2011). While global research emphasizes workforce training, equipment reliability, and leadership commitment as critical to fire safety, there is a paucity of Nigeria-specific studies addressing the interplay of workforce demographics, operational complexities, and regulatory compliance. This research fills this gap by providing an assessment of fire safety practices, focusing on employee awareness, safety infrastructure, and organizational commitment within Nigeria's unique operational landscape.

This study aims to evaluate the current state of fire preparedness and mitigation strategies in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, with the goal of identifying critical areas for improvement to enhance fire safety practices and procedures. By evaluating the level of awareness and training among employees, the research seeks to determine their familiarity with fire safety protocols and their perceived readiness to respond to emergencies, addressing the question of how well-prepared the workforce is to handle fire

incidents. Through testing hypotheses on the relationships between employee familiarity, muster point availability, drill regularity, regulatory compliance, and environmental concerns, the research aims to uncover statistical correlations that inform targeted interventions.

Research Methodology

Study Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design to evaluate fire preparedness and mitigation strategies in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. The design was selected because it enables the collection of data at a single point in time, providing information into employee awareness, safety infrastructure, management commitment, and regulatory compliance. While primarily quantitative, the study also incorporated limited qualitative feedback from open-ended questions to enrich interpretation of results.

Study Population and Sampling

The study population consisted of employees actively engaged in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, including operational staff, safety officers, administrative personnel, and management representatives across selected crude oil facilities. The inclusion of individuals from different organizational levels was intended to capture diverse perspectives and provide a holistic understanding of fire safety practices and preparedness within the sector. The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane formula for finite populations (Tepping, 1968), expressed as:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)} \quad (1)$$

where n is the required sample size, N is the estimated population, and e is the margin of error (0.05). Based on an estimated workforce of approximately 400 employees across the selected facilities, the formula yielded a minimum sample size of 250. To increase representativeness and account for potential non-response, the target was adjusted upward to 350 respondents.

Questionnaires were distributed electronically via Google Forms, of which 211 valid responses were retrieved, giving a response rate of 60%. Although lower than the targeted sample, this size was considered adequate for statistical analysis and provided sufficient variation across roles, experience levels, and facilities to ensure meaningful insights into fire preparedness and mitigation within the Nigerian oil and gas industry.

2.3 Data Collection Instrument

Data was collected using a structured questionnaire designed to capture demographic characteristics, fire safety awareness, availability and functionality of safety infrastructure, hazard management practices, and emergency response protocols. The instrument was adapted from prior safety studies and modified for contextual relevance. It comprised both closed-ended items on a five-point Likert scale and multiple-choice questions, with an additional section for open-ended comments. A pilot test involving 15 respondents was conducted to assess clarity and reliability, leading to minor revisions in wording.

Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaire was distributed electronically via Google Forms to enhance accessibility for geographically dispersed respondents. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained before completion. Respondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality, with data used strictly for academic purposes.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (IBM SPSS, version 25). Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize demographic profiles and key responses. Inferential statistics were conducted using Chi-square tests to assess associations between variables such as work experience, training frequency, and perceived effectiveness of fire safety measures. Open-ended responses were subjected to thematic analysis to provide qualitative context to quantitative findings.

Validity, Reliability, and Ethics

Instrument validity was enhanced through expert review and pilot testing, while internal reliability was assessed using consistency checks across related questionnaire items. This study was conducted in accordance with ethical principles, ensuring voluntary participation and obtaining informed consent from all participants. All data were anonymized prior to analysis to protect confidentiality. Formal approval was granted by the Department of Environmental Management and Toxicology, Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun, as well as by the management of the participating facilities from which the data were sourced.

Methodological Limitations

The study relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to recall bias or social desirability bias. In addition, findings are context-specific to selected oil and gas facilities in Nigeria and may not be generalizable to the entire industry. Nonetheless, the sample size and diversity of respondents across job functions enhance the representativeness of the results.

Results and Discussion

Socio-Demography of Respondents

The socio-demographic profile of respondents provides important context for understanding fire preparedness in the Nigerian oil and gas industry as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Distribution of Respondents

	Category	Percentage (%)
<i>Age (years)</i>	18–25	4.4
	26–35	19.1
	36–45	44.1
	46–55	25
	56 and above	7.4
<i>Marital Status</i>	Single	20.6
	Married	75
	Divorced	3.4
	Widowed	1
<i>Educational Qualification</i>	High school	4.4
	HND/Bachelor's degree	52.9
	Master's degree	36.8
	PhD	4.4
<i>Years of Experience</i>	0–5 years	13.3
	6–10 years	13.3
	11–15 years	24.4
	16–20 years	24.6
	Over 20 years	24.4

The socio-demographic analysis of respondents revealed that the majority (44.1%) were aged 36–45 years, followed by 25% in the 46–55-year range, 19.1% aged 26–35, 4.4% aged 18–25, and 7.4% aged 56 years or older. Marital status data showed that 75% of respondents were married, 20.6% single, 3.4% divorced, and 1% widowed. Educational attainment was relatively high, with 52.9% holding HND/Bachelor’s degrees, 36.8% master’s degrees, and 4.4% each reporting PhDs or high school education. Work experience was broadly distributed: 24.6% reported 16–20 years of service, 24.4% more than 20 years, 24.4% between 11–15 years, and the remaining respondents had 0–10 years of experience. These results indicate a workforce dominated by mid-career professionals with substantial experience, predominantly married, and well-educated, reflecting a combination of stability, knowledge, and analytical capacity within the sector.

The implications of these findings are significant for fire preparedness in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. The dominance of mid-career professionals suggests a workforce with extensive industry knowledge and adaptability to challenging conditions such as offshore deployments, consistent with findings by (Bukth & Fatima, 2024). The high proportion of married employees may contribute to stability and responsibility, enhancing adherence to safety protocols, while single employees may bring focused attention to safety tasks, as similarly observed by (Williams, 2018). The well-educated nature of the workforce implies strong critical thinking and problem-solving capabilities, which are essential for implementing effective fire safety measures, supporting observations (Quaigrain et al., 2024). Furthermore, the diverse work experience distribution ensures a balance between fresh perspectives and long-standing expertise, reinforcing fire safety practices, as noted in (Carrillo, 2004). Taken together, the socio-demographic characteristics highlight a workforce dominated by educated, mid-career, and married professionals with substantial experience. This profile implies a strong foundation for fostering a robust safety culture, while also signaling the need for targeted training to address the unique needs of younger entrants and older workers. Compared to similar studies, these results confirm the maturity and stability of the oil and gas workforce in Nigeria, which has important implications for sustaining and enhancing fire preparedness strategies across the industry.

Fire Safety Awareness and Training

Understanding fire safety awareness and training among workers in the Nigerian oil and gas industry is critical to evaluating the sector’s overall preparedness and risk mitigation capacity. Effective fire preparedness depends not only on the availability of safety equipment and infrastructure but also on workers’ familiarity with procedures, confidence in responding to emergencies, and consistent participation in training programs. In this study we evaluated respondents’ knowledge of fire safety procedures, perceived adequacy of training, access to fire safety equipment, awareness of designated muster points, and installation of fire prevention gadgets. These dimensions collectively provide information into the strengths and gaps in the industry’s fire safety culture, highlighting areas that require targeted interventions to enhance workforce readiness, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Fire Safety Awareness and Training of Respondents

Indicator	Response Category	Percentage (%)
<i>Familiarity with Fire Safety Procedures</i>	Familiar	58
	Uncertain	35
	Not familiar	7
<i>Adequacy of Fire Emergency Training</i>	Agree / Strongly Agree	76.2
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	23.8
<i>Access to Fire Safety Equipment</i>	Agree / Strongly Agree	82.25
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	17.75
<i>Awareness of Designated Muster Points</i>	Agree / Strongly Agree	82.02
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	17.98

<i>Installation of Fire Prevention Gadgets</i>	Agree / Strongly Agree	86.1
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	13.9
<i>Regular Fire Safety Training Sessions</i>	Agree / Strongly Agree	82.25
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	17.75

The survey results on fire safety awareness and training among workers in the Nigerian oil and gas industry reveal a mixed but generally positive picture. While 58% reported being familiar with basic procedures, 35% were uncertain, and 7% indicated no familiarity. Regarding perceived adequacy of fire emergency training, 76.2% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they felt adequately trained, whereas 23.8% disagreed, highlighting a segment of the workforce that may require additional instruction or reinforcement. Access to fire safety equipment was largely perceived as adequate, with 82.25% affirming availability, though 17.75% reported limited access. Similarly, 82.02% acknowledged the presence of designated muster points, while 17.98% disagreed or were unsure. Installation of fire prevention gadgets, including alarms and extinguishers, was recognized by 86.1% of respondents, leaving 13.9% expressing disagreement. Finally, 82.25% of participants reported that regular fire safety training sessions were conducted at their facilities, while 17.75% indicated irregularities or gaps in training frequency. This is consistent with previous studies emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to improve fire preparedness in industrial settings (Chen et al., 2015; Longo et al., 2019; Benson et al., 2024).

The implications of these results are multidimensional. The majority’s acknowledgment of regular training sessions and adequate safety infrastructure suggests that current fire preparedness programs provide a solid foundation for emergency response, particularly given the demographic distribution of respondents—predominantly mid-career employees aged 36–55 years, likely possessing sufficient industry experience to benefit from structured safety training. However, the observed gaps among the minorities indicate potential vulnerabilities in overall workforce readiness, which could compromise coordinated responses during fire incidents. Addressing these disparities requires systematic efforts, including needs assessments to identify specific training deficiencies, the development of tailored programs to enhance both procedural knowledge and hands-on competence, and regular evaluations to ensure continuous improvement. Ensuring uniform and frequent fire safety training across all workforce segments is crucial for fostering a well-prepared, cohesive, and resilient workforce capable of minimizing fire-related risks (Asad et al., 2022; McGee & Russell, 2003).

Fire Safety Measures and Preparedness

Evaluating fire safety measures and preparedness within the Nigerian oil and gas industry is essential for understanding the sector’s ability to prevent, respond to, and mitigate fire-related incidents. As shown in Table 3, an examination of existing safety infrastructure, procedural compliance, and emergency response mechanisms provides information into the strengths and potential vulnerabilities across facilities. Such an assessment is critical for identifying areas where interventions, standardization, and training can enhance the industry’s overall fire resilience. In this survey we looked at multiple dimensions of fire safety measures, including the presence of fire safety plans, regular drills, alarm testing, maintenance of suppression systems, clearly marked exit routes, and emergency response teams.

Table 3. Fire Safety Measures and Preparedness of Facilities in the Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry

Fire Safety Measure	Response Category	Percentage (%)
<i>Facility has a Fire Safety Plan</i>	Agree	61.5
	Strongly Agree	23.5
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	15
<i>Regular Fire Safety Drills</i>	Agree	61
	Strongly Agree	24

	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	15
<i>Fire Alarm System Tested Regularly</i>	Agree	56
	Strongly Agree	26
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	18
<i>Fire Suppression System Maintained</i>	Agree	58
	Strongly Agree	24.5
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	17.5
<i>Clearly Marked Exit Routes</i>	Agree	63
	Strongly Agree	22
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	15
<i>Emergency Response Teams in Place</i>	Agree	62.5
	Strongly Agree	20
	Disagree / Strongly Disagree	17.5

The survey revealed that 61.5% of respondents agreed and 23.5% strongly agreed that their facilities have a fire safety plan in place, although 15% expressed disagreement or strong disagreement. Regular fire drills were affirmed by 85.5% of respondents, with 15% indicating their absence. Regarding fire alarm systems, 56% agreed and 26% strongly agreed that alarms were regularly tested, while 18% disagreed or strongly disagreed. Maintenance and inspection of fire suppression systems were confirmed by 82.5% of respondents, leaving 17.5% with reservations. Clearly marked exit routes were acknowledged by 85% of participants (63% agree, 22% strongly agree), with 15% expressing disagreement. Lastly, 82.5% of respondents confirmed the presence of emergency response teams in their facilities, while 17.5% reported their absence or insufficiency. Collectively, these results highlight both commendable practices and areas requiring improvement within the Nigerian oil and gas sector.

The predominance of positive responses indicates a general adherence to structured fire safety measures and a proactive approach toward preparedness, suggesting that the workforce is largely familiar with fire prevention and response protocols. However, the presence of dissenting opinions across all parameters points to potential inconsistencies in implementation or communication of fire safety measures. These gaps could compromise emergency responsiveness, particularly in facilities with less experienced or younger workers, who may rely more heavily on structured guidance and training (Brkić, 2025; Brkić & Praks, 2021). Ensuring uniform compliance across facilities, including standardized drills, regular testing of alarms and suppression systems, clearly marked exit routes, and functioning emergency response teams, is vital. Addressing these gaps through targeted training, policy reinforcement, and continuous monitoring could strengthen fire resilience and minimize risks to personnel and assets. Comparatively, these findings align with previous studies emphasizing that fire preparedness is contingent not only on equipment availability but also on consistent procedural implementation and workforce engagement (Flin et al., 1996; Jennings, 2020).

Fire Prevention and Hazard Management

Assessing fire prevention and hazard management practices within the Nigerian oil and gas industry provides information into the sector's proactive measures to minimize fire risks. This includes housekeeping practices, storage of flammable materials, implementation of hazard management systems, maintenance of electrical equipment, and utilization of fire-resistant barriers or materials. Table 4 presents the distribution of responses on fire prevention and hazard management practices among respondents in the Nigerian oil and gas industry.

The survey results indicate generally positive perceptions of fire prevention and hazard management measures within the industry. A substantial majority of respondents agreed or strongly agreed that their facilities maintain good housekeeping practices (82.8%), store flammable materials safely (83.9%), have effective hazard identification systems (82.7%), conduct regular maintenance of electrical equipment (84.8%), and implement fire-resistant barriers or materials (82.9–83.8%). Despite this overall positive sentiment, dissenting responses ranging from 15.2% to 17.9% across different measures reveal potential

gaps in the consistency, coverage, and awareness of these practices. These variations suggest that while many facilities have established preventive measures, there is room for improvement in standardization and enforcement.

Table 4. Distribution of Respondents' Perceptions on Fire Prevention and Hazard Management Practices in Nigerian Oil and Gas Facilities, Highlighting Levels of Agreement and Dissent Across Six Key Safety Measures

Fire Prevention Measure	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
<i>Housekeeping practices</i>	24.4	58.4	7.3	9.9
<i>Safe storage of flammable materials</i>	23.8	60.1	5.6	10.5
<i>Hazard identification & management system</i>	23.4	59.3	8	9.4
<i>Regular maintenance & inspection of electrical equipment</i>	22.4	62.4	9.8	5.4
<i>Implementation of fire-resistant barriers/materials</i>	25	57.1	7.7	10.2
<i>Use of fire-resistant barriers/materials (Figure 4.4.6)</i>	23.2	60.6	5.15	5.15

The findings show the importance of robust fire prevention and hazard management strategies in safeguarding personnel, assets, and operations within the Nigerian oil and gas sector. High levels of agreement on housekeeping, storage, hazard management systems, electrical maintenance, and fire-resistant barriers indicate an overall awareness and commitment to fire safety, which aligns with global best practices in industrial safety management (Gravit, Dmitriev, et al., 2024; Gravit et al., 2018; Gravit, Prusakov, et al., 2024). However, the presence of dissenting opinions suggests potential vulnerabilities in certain facilities, which may compromise overall resilience to fire incidents. These gaps may stem from differences in facility size, workforce experience, training, or resource allocation. Moreover, the demographic profile of respondents, primarily mid-career professionals (36–55 years) implies that fire safety initiatives are reaching experienced personnel but may require greater engagement with younger or less experienced staff to ensure awareness and adherence across all organizational levels.

Fire Safety and Incident Assessment

Assessing fire safety and incident response within the Nigerian oil and gas industry provides critical insight into the effectiveness of existing emergency plans, employee response, suppression systems, and communication protocols. Key aspects include the perceived efficacy of fire safety plans, employees' ability to respond to fires, performance of fire suppression systems, incidence of injuries or fatalities, muster point utilization, and communication system functionality during fire events. Table 5 presents the distribution of respondents' perceptions on fire safety and incident assessment in Nigerian oil and gas facilities, highlighting levels of agreement and dissent across six key measures.

Table 5. Distribution of Respondents' Perceptions on Fire Safety and Incident Assessment in Nigerian Oil and Gas Facilities, Highlighting Levels of Agreement and Dissent Across Six Key Measures

Fire Safety Measure	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
<i>Effectiveness of fire safety plans</i>	22.8	61.4	6.4	9.4
<i>Employee fire response effectiveness</i>	23.7	59.7	8.1	8.5
<i>Effectiveness of fire suppression systems</i>	9.6	62.1	3.6	5.4

<i>Occurrence of injuries or fatalities</i>	25.5	54.5	9.5	10.5
<i>Effectiveness of muster points</i>	24.8	58.2	7	10
<i>Functionality of communication systems during fire</i>	23.1	60.9	5.8	10.2

The survey results indicate a predominantly positive perception of fire safety and incident response among respondents. The majority of participants expressed confidence in the effectiveness of their facilities' fire safety plans (84.2%), employee response effectiveness (83.4%), and the operational performance of fire suppression systems (71.7%). Similarly, respondents generally affirmed the adequacy of muster points (83%) and communication systems (84%) during fire events. Despite this overall optimism, a portion of respondents acknowledged the occurrence of injuries or fatalities (80%), and dissenting opinions ranged between 5.4% and 15.8% across all measures, suggesting areas of concern and variability in the implementation or awareness of fire safety protocols.

These findings suggest that while the Nigerian oil and gas workforce generally perceives fire safety and incident response systems as effective, there remain gaps that could affect resilience during emergencies. The high level of positive responses reflects trust in established safety measures, which aligns with similar studies in the sector that report strong confidence in structured fire safety plans and employee preparedness (Alsehaimi et al., 2025; Hosseinnia Davatgar et al., 2021). Conversely, the substantial acknowledgment of injuries or fatalities indicates persistent vulnerabilities that require targeted interventions, such as enhanced emergency drills, improved fire suppression maintenance, and reinforcement of communication protocols. The demographic composition of respondents, largely mid-career professionals; may influence these perceptions, as more experienced workers often report higher confidence in safety protocols (Kent, 2003).

Management Commitment to Fire Prevention and Mitigation Strategies

Assessing respondents' perceptions of management commitment provides insight into organizational dedication to fire safety and preparedness. The study explored leadership commitment, employee engagement, presence of dedicated fire safety officers, management-led training, documented fire safety policies, and transparency in communication channels. Table 7 presents the distribution of responses on management commitment to fire prevention and mitigation strategies among respondents in Nigerian oil and gas facilities, highlighting levels of agreement and dissent across six key measures.

Table 7. Distribution of Respondents' Perceptions on Management Commitment to Fire Prevention and Mitigation Strategies in Nigerian Oil and Gas Facilities, Highlighting Levels of Agreement and Dissent across Six Key Measures

Measure	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
<i>Leadership commitment to fire safety</i>	30	62	3	5
<i>Employee engagement in fire safety</i>	28	59	6	7
<i>Presence of designated fire safety officer/team</i>	27	60	5	8
<i>Regular meetings/training on fire safety with management involvement</i>	29	58	5	8
<i>Existence of documented fire safety policy endorsed by top management</i>	26	64	4	6
<i>Transparency of communication channels for reporting fire safety concerns</i>	21	44	5	7

The survey indicated a generally positive perception of management commitment to fire safety. A combined 92% of respondents acknowledged leadership dedication to fire safety, while 87% recognized

employee engagement in fire prevention practices. Similarly, 87% confirmed the presence of a designated fire safety officer or team with decision-making authority, and 87% agreed or strongly agreed that regular management-led training or meetings occur. Additionally, 90% acknowledged the existence of documented fire safety policies endorsed by top management, and 65% affirmed transparency in communication channels for reporting fire safety concerns. Despite these positive perceptions, a minority (ranging from 3% to 12%) expressed disagreement or strong disagreement across these measures, indicating potential variability in implementation or awareness across facilities.

The results indicate that the Nigerian oil and gas workforce perceives strong management commitment, which is crucial for fostering a safety culture that supports proactive fire prevention and mitigation. High agreement rates regarding leadership commitment, employee engagement, and the presence of fire safety officers align with studies highlighting the importance of top-down support in enhancing workplace safety compliance and incident responsiveness (Iqbal et al., 2019; Kvalheim & Dahl, 2016). The minority expressing dissent indicates the need for consistent communication, regular training reinforcement, and clear implementation of fire safety policies to ensure uniform commitment across all facilities. Transparent channels for reporting fire safety concerns are particularly important, as they facilitate employee participation in safety improvements and strengthen overall fire preparedness strategies (Lindøe et al., 2011). Management commitment, as perceived by respondents, provides a foundation for continuous improvement, reinforcing organizational readiness and resilience to fire incidents within the Nigerian oil and gas industry.

Fire Outbreak Response and Post-Incident Assessment

Participants' perceptions of fire outbreak response and post-incident assessment provide critical insights into the preparedness of facilities in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. The study assessed the existence of evacuation procedures, assigned roles, communication systems, accounting mechanisms, post-fire restrictions, formal assessments, medical support, and lessons learned processes. Table 8 shows respondents' views on these measures, highlighting levels of agreement and dissent.

Table 8. Distribution of Respondents' Perceptions on Fire Outbreak Response and Post-Incident Assessment in Nigerian Oil and Gas Facilities

Measure	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
<i>Existence of designated evacuation procedures</i>	33	57	6	4
<i>Established roles/responsibilities during fire outbreak</i>	27	44	5	3
<i>Effectiveness of communication systems during fire outbreak</i>	34	54	7	5
<i>Accounting system for all employees during evacuation</i>	34.5	55.5	6.5	3.5
<i>Post-fire incident measures (preventing re-entry)</i>	28	47	5	3
<i>Formal post-incident assessment process</i>	32	60	5	3
<i>Provision of medical assistance or counselling</i>	31	62	5	2
<i>Process for reporting/documenting lessons learned</i>	34	58	5.5	2.5

The survey indicates generally positive perceptions of fire outbreak response and post-incident assessment procedures. A combined 90% of participants acknowledged the existence of structured evacuation procedures, while 71% recognized clear roles and responsibilities during fire outbreaks. Communication systems were perceived as effective by 88% of respondents, and 90% confirmed the presence of an accounting system for personnel. Post-incident measures, including preventing premature

re-entry, were affirmed by 75%, and formal post-incident assessments were recognized by 92%. Medical assistance or counselling mechanisms were acknowledged by 93%, and 92% agreed that lessons learned are documented and implemented. Minor disagreement (ranging from 2% to 10%) across these measures indicates potential variability in protocol awareness or implementation across facilities.

The results reflect a substantial level of preparedness and organizational structure in fire outbreak response and post-incident procedures. High agreement rates regarding evacuation procedures, assigned roles, communication systems, and personnel accounting indicate effective operational planning and employee safety prioritization (Crichton & Flin, 2001). Similarly, positive responses regarding post-incident assessments, medical support, and lessons learned processes suggest a commitment to continuous improvement and organizational learning following fire events. However, the presence of dissenting opinions, albeit a minority, highlights areas requiring attention, including consistent communication, regular drills, and reinforcement of post-incident measures. Ensuring that all personnel are aware of and adhere to established procedures will strengthen fire preparedness, mitigate risks, and enhance the industry's resilience to fire incidents. The results of the survey indicates the importance of integrating post-incident assessment, personnel support, and lessons learned into broader fire safety strategies to promote a robust safety culture in the Nigerian oil and gas sector.

Association Between Worker Experience, Fire Safety Practices, and Preparedness Measures in the Nigerian Oil and Gas Industry

To examine the relationships between various aspects of fire preparedness and mitigation in the Nigerian oil and gas industry, a chi-square (χ^2) analysis was conducted. This statistical method enables the assessment of associations between categorical variables, providing insights into how workers' experience, familiarity with fire safety procedures, effectiveness in managing fire incidents, and the presence of essential fire safety measures are interrelated. By applying this approach, the study identified significant patterns and potential gaps in fire safety practices across facilities, thereby informing targeted interventions and policy recommendations. The results of this analysis are shown in Table 11, providing key information into significant associations and potential gaps in fire safety practices across different facilities.

Table 11. Chi-Square Analysis of Fire Preparedness and Mitigation Measures

Items	Years of experience working in the Nigerian oil and gas industry	Workers familiarity with fire safety procedures	Effectiveness on managing fire incident	Fire Contingency Plan in place
My facility has a fire safety plan in place	$\chi^2 = 8.729$ $df = 3$ P-value= (0.033)***	$\chi^2 = 4.198$ $df = 3$ P-value= (0.241)	$\chi^2 = 21.157$ $df = 9$ P-value= (0.012)***	$\chi^2 = 9.472$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.149)
Are there regular fire safety drills conducted in your facility to test emergency response procedures	$\chi^2 = 11.224$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.081)***	$\chi^2 = 12.515$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.051)*	$\chi^2 = 21.884$ $df = 9$ P-value= (0.009)***	$\chi^2 = 6.032$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.420)
My facility has a fire alarm system that is tested regularly	$\chi^2 = 4.287$ $df = 3$ P-value= (0.232)	$\chi^2 = 2.323$ $df = 3$ P-value= (0.508)	$\chi^2 = 35.246$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.000)***	$\chi^2 = 12.379$ $df = 4$ P-value= (0.015)**
My facility has a fire suppression system that is maintained and inspected regularly.	$\chi^2 = 0.536$ $df = 3$ P-value= (0.911)	$\chi^2 = 10.959$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.090)*	$\chi^2 = 15.373$ $df = 9$ P-value= (0.081)*	$\chi^2 = 3.132$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.792)
My facility has good housekeeping practices in place to reduce the risk of fire.	$\chi^2 = 5.717$ $df = 3$ P-value= (0.126)	$\chi^2 = 25.426$ $df = 6$	$\chi^2 = 37.825$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.000)***	$\chi^2 = 7.8$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.253)

		P-value= (0.000)***		
Are there fire-resistant barriers or materials used to minimize the spread of fire within your facility	$\chi^2 = 10.922$ $df = 3$ P-value= (0.012)***	$\chi^2 = 25.426$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.000)	$\chi^2 = 4.672$ $df = 9$ P-value= (0.862)	$\chi^2 = 8.995$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.174)
Inspection with relevant Regulatory authorities	$\chi^2 = 2.017$ $df = 3$ P-value= (0.558)	$\chi^2 = 33.507$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.000)***	$\chi^2 = 12.385$ $df = 9$ P-value= (0.192)	$\chi^2 = 8.810$ $df = 6$ P-value= (0.185)
Note: “***” significant at 1%, “**” significant at 5%, “*” significant at 10%				

The analysis revealed several statistically significant relationships. A significant correlation exists between years of experience and workers’ familiarity with fire safety procedures ($\chi^2=8.729$, $p=0.033^{***}$), suggesting that accumulated experience enhances knowledge of safety protocols. Years of experience were also highly associated with the presence of a Fire Contingency Plan ($\chi^2=21.157$, $p=0.012^{***}$), indicating that more experienced personnel may influence the adoption of structured fire preparedness measures. Regular fire safety drills showed a significant relationship with workers’ familiarity with fire procedures ($\chi^2=11.224$, $p=0.081^*$), and were highly associated with the presence of a Fire Contingency Plan ($\chi^2=21.884$, $p=0.009^{***}$), highlighting the value of drills in promoting preparedness. Similarly, facilities that test fire suppression systems regularly are more likely to have effective incident management ($\chi^2=12.379$, $p=0.015^{**}$) and established contingency plans ($\chi^2=35.246$, $p=0.000^{***}$), underscoring the importance of equipment maintenance in operational readiness.

Some measures, however, did not show significant associations. For instance, years of experience was not significantly correlated with the effectiveness of managing fire incidents ($\chi^2=4.198$, $p=0.241$), and good housekeeping practices were not significantly related to workers’ familiarity with safety procedures ($\chi^2=5.717$, $p=0.126$). These findings suggest that while experience and procedural drills enhance awareness and preparedness, they may not directly translate into more effective incident management without complementary training and enforcement of protocols.

The chi-square analysis emphasizes that both human factors (experience, familiarity) and organizational practices (drills, equipment maintenance) are critical for effective fire preparedness and mitigation. Facilities should prioritize continuous training, regular drills, and systematic maintenance of fire safety systems to strengthen overall readiness. Moreover, implementing and reinforcing Fire Contingency Plans, along with periodic evaluations, can enhance resilience and minimize the risk of fire-related incidents in the Nigerian oil and gas industry (Kitimbo et al., 2025).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the Nigerian oil and gas industry has made commendable progress in fire preparedness and mitigation, with strong evidence of employee awareness, availability of safety infrastructure, and management commitment. Yet, persistent gaps in training adequacy, clarity of safety procedures, and uniform implementation of contingency measures reveal vulnerabilities that could compromise emergency response. The significant associations between workforce experience, fire drills, and the effectiveness of contingency plans highlight the crucial role of continuous training and operational readiness in shaping fire resilience. To advance beyond the current state, the industry must adopt a holistic approach that integrates regular, standardized drills, routine maintenance of fire suppression systems, advanced detection technologies, and transparent communication channels. Equally important is sustained regulatory oversight to ensure compliance across all facilities. Embedding post-incident assessments and environmental safeguards into safety protocols will further reduce risks while supporting Nigeria’s broader economic and sustainability goals. By strengthening these measures, the

industry can build a resilient safety culture that protects lives, secures vital infrastructure, and minimizes ecological harm, thereby reinforcing both national stability and global confidence in Nigeria's energy sector.

References

- Abu, R., Patchigolla, K., & Simms, N. (2023). A Review on Qualitative Assessment of Natural Gas Utilisation Options for Eliminating Routine Nigerian Gas Flaring. *Gases*, 3(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.3390/gases3010001>
- Alsehaimi, A., Waqar, A., Radu, D., Bratu, C., Almujiabah, H., & Benjeddou, O. (2025). A framework for enhancing safety planning in oil and gas construction projects. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 16(2), 103257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2024.103257>
- Ambituuni, A., Amezaga, J., & Emesch, E. (2014). Analysis of safety and environmental regulations for downstream petroleum industry operations in Nigeria: Problems and prospects. *Environmental Development*, 9, 43–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2013.12.002>
- Asad, M. M., Sherwani, F., Hassan, R. B., Sahito, Z., & Khan, N. (2022). Workforce safety education and training for oil and gas industry: A conceptual framework for virtual reality-based HAZFO expert 2.0. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 20(5), 1122–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEDT-08-2020-0330>
- Babalola, A. A., & Olawuyi, D. S. (2022). Overcoming Regulatory Failure in the Design and Implementation of Gas Flaring Policies: The Potential and Promise of an Energy Justice Approach. *Sustainability*, 14(11), 6800. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14116800>
- Benson, C., Obasi, I. C., Akinwande, D. V., & Ile, C. (2024). The impact of interventions on health, safety and environment in the process industry. *Heliyon*, 10(1), e23604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23604>
- Brkić, D. (2025). Fire Hazards Caused by Equipment Used in Offshore Oil and Gas Operations: Prescriptive vs. Goal-Oriented Legislation. *Fire*, 8(1), 29. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fire8010029>
- Brkić, D., & Praks, P. (2021). Probability Analysis and Prevention of Offshore Oil and Gas Accidents: Fire as a Cause and a Consequence. *Fire*, 4(4), 71. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fire4040071>
- Bukth, T., & Fatima, K. (2024). The Influence of Job Characteristics on the Motivation and Satisfaction of Mid-Career Professionals. *Psychology*, 15(11), 1760–1790. <https://doi.org/10.4236/psych.2024.1511103>
- Carrillo, P. (2004). Managing knowledge: Lessons from the oil and gas sector. *Construction Management and Economics*, 22(6), 631–642. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144619042000226289>
- Chen, H., Pittman, W. C., Hatanaka, L. C., Harding, B. Z., Boussouf, A., Moore, D. A., Milke, J. A., & Mannan, M. S. (2015). Integration of process safety engineering and fire protection engineering for better safety performance. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 37, 74–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlpi.2015.06.013>
- Crichton, M., & Flin, R. (2001). Training for emergency management: Tactical decision games. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 88(2–3), 255–266. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3894\(01\)00270-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3894(01)00270-9)
- Dhali, M., Hassan, S., & Subramaniam, U. (2023). Comparative Analysis of Oil and Gas Legal Frameworks in Bangladesh and Nigeria: A Pathway towards Achieving Sustainable Energy through Policy. *Sustainability*, 15(21), 15228. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su152115228>
- Fadeyibi, I. O., Jewo, P. I., Opoola, P., Babalola, O. S., Ugburo, A., & Ademiluyi, S. A. (2011). Burns and fire disasters from leaking petroleum pipes in Lagos, Nigeria: An 8-year experience. *Burns*, 37(1), 145–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.burns.2010.06.012>

- Fetisov, V., Gonopolsky, A. M., Davardoost, H., Ghanbari, A. R., & Mohammadi, A. H. (2023). Regulation and impact of VOC and CO₂ emissions on low-carbon energy systems resilient to climate change: A case study on an environmental issue in the oil and gas industry. *Energy Science & Engineering*, 11(4), 1516–1535. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ese3.1383>
- Flin, R., Slaven, G., & Stewart, K. (1996). Emergency Decision Making in the Offshore Oil and Gas Industry. *Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, 38(2), 262–277. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872089606380207>
- Gravit, M., Dmitriev, I., Shcheglov, N., & Radaev, A. (2024). Oil and Gas Structures: Forecasting the Fire Resistance of Steel Structures with Fire Protection under Hydrocarbon Fire Conditions. *Fire*, 7(6), 173. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fire7060173>
- Gravit, M., Gumerova, E., Bardin, A., & Lukinov, V. (2018). Increase of Fire Resistance Limits of Building Structures of Oil-and-Gas Complex Under Hydrocarbon Fire. In V. Murgul & Z. Popovic (Eds.), *International Scientific Conference Energy Management of Municipal Transportation Facilities and Transport EMMFT 2017* (Vol. 692, pp. 818–829). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-70987-1_87
- Gravit, M., Prusakov, V., Shcheglov, N., & Kotlyarskaya, I. (2024). Fire Protection of Steel Structures of Oil and Gas Facilities: Multilayer, Removable, Non-Combustible Covers. *Fire*, 7(3), 86. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fire7030086>
- Hassan, A. I., & Saleh, H. M. (2022). Toxicity and hazardous waste regulations. In *Hazardous Waste Management* (pp. 165–182). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-824344-2.00012-4>
- Hassan, A. S. (2021). Asymmetric effects of oil revenue on government expenditure: Insights from oil-exporting developing countries. *OPEC Energy Review*, 45(2), 257–274. <https://doi.org/10.1111/opec.12203>
- Horn, S. A., & Dasgupta, P. K. (2024). The Air Quality Index (AQI) in historical and analytical perspective a tutorial review. *Talanta*, 267, 125260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2023.125260>
- Hosseinnia Davatgar, B., Paltrinieri, N., & Bubbico, R. (2021). Safety Barrier Management: Risk-Based Approach for the Oil and Gas Sector. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 9(7), 722. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9070722>
- Iqbal, H., Waheed, B., Haider, H., Tesfamariam, S., & Sadiq, R. (2019). Mapping safety culture attributes with integrity management program to achieve assessment goals: A framework for oil and gas pipelines industry. *Journal of Safety Research*, 68, 59–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2018.12.010>
- Jennings, M. (2020). The oil and gas industry, the competence assessment of Offshore Installation Managers (OIMs) and Control Room Operators (CROs) in emergency response, and the lack of effective assessment of underpinning technical knowledge and understanding. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 65, 104090. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlp.2020.104090>
- Kent, J. A. (2003). Managing an Emergency Preparedness Program. In J. A. Kent (Ed.), *Riegel's Handbook of Industrial Chemistry* (pp. 146–176). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-23816-6_6
- Kerin, T. (2016). The evolution of process safety standards and legislation following landmark events-what have we learnt? *Process Safety Progress*, 35(2), 165–170. <https://doi.org/10.1002/prs.11762>
- Kitimbo, M., Timothy, O., Oloa, H., & Mutesasira, B. (2025). Design and Fabrication of an Automated Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) Fire Suppression System. *World Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 13(02), 179–214. <https://doi.org/10.4236/wjet.2025.132012>
- Kvalheim, S. A., & Dahl, Ø. (2016). Safety compliance and safety climate: A repeated cross-sectional study in the oil and gas industry. *Journal of Safety Research*, 59, 33–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsr.2016.10.006>

- Lindøe, P. H., Engen, O. A., & Olsen, O. E. (2011). Responses to accidents in different industrial sectors. *Safety Science*, 49(1), 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2009.12.007>
- Longo, F., Nicoletti, L., & Padovano, A. (2019). Emergency preparedness in industrial plants: A forward-looking solution based on industry 4.0 enabling technologies. *Computers in Industry*, 105, 99–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2018.12.003>
- McGee, T. K., & Russell, S. (2003). “It’s just a natural way of life...” an investigation of wildfire preparedness in rural Australia. *Environmental Hazards*, 5(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hazards.2003.04.001>
- Miche, R., Mueller, S., Schneider, R., Wahren, S., & Hornberger, M. (2015). Integrated hazardous materials management: Combining requirements from various environmental legislations to enable effective business compliance processes in industries. *International Journal of Precision Engineering and Manufacturing-Green Technology*, 2(3), 289–298. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40684-015-0035-6>
- Nwankwo, C. D., Arewa, A. O., Theophilus, S. C., & Esenowo, V. N. (2022). Analysis of accidents caused by human factors in the oil and gas industry using the HFACS-OGI framework. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 28(3), 1642–1654. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803548.2021.1916238>
- Olujobi, O. J., & Ape, N. T. (2025). Reforming legal frameworks for combating gas flaring in Nigeria: A comparative legal analysis and sustainable solutions. *Resources Policy*, 109, 105721. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2025.105721>
- Oluyemi, O. A. (2020). The Military Dimension of Niger Delta Crisis and Its Implications on Nigeria National Security. *Sage Open*, 10(2), 2158244020922895. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020922895>
- Quaigrain, R. A., Owusu-Manu, D.-G., Edwards, D. J., Hammond, M., Hammond, M., & Martek, I. (2024). Occupational health and safety orientation in the oil and gas industry of Ghana: Analysis of knowledge and attitudinal influences on compliance. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 22(3), 795–812. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEDT-11-2021-0664>
- Slil, E., Iyiola, K., Alzubi, A., & Aljuhmani, H. Y. (2025). Impact of Safety Leadership and Employee Morale on Safety Performance: The Moderating Role of Harmonious Safety Passion. *Buildings*, 15(2), 186. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings15020186>
- Srivastava, R. K. (2020). Towards Risk Resilient Urbanization. In R. K. Srivastava, *Managing Urbanization, Climate Change and Disasters in South Asia* (pp. 359–434). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-2410-3_8
- Tepping, B. J. (1968). Elementary Sampling Theory, *Taro Yamane*. Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc., 1967. Pp. x–405. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 63(322), 728–730. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1968.11009297>
- Tsai, C.-H., Shen, Y.-H., & Tsai, W.-T. (2021). Sustainable Material Management of Industrial Hazardous Waste in Taiwan: Case Studies in Circular Economy. *Sustainability*, 13(16), 9410. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13169410>
- Williams, C. L. (2018). The Gendered Discourse of Work-Family Balance in the Oil and Gas Industry. *Social Currents*, 5(2), 120–139. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2329496517748334>
- Wood, D. A., Nwaoha, C., & Towler, B. F. (2012). Gas-to-liquids (GTL): A review of an industry offering several routes for monetizing natural gas. *Journal of Natural Gas Science and Engineering*, 9, 196–208. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jngse.2012.07.001>